

Determination of Energy Dependence Level Density Parameter and its Application in Fission Products Calculation of Pu-238

Abdul Waris^{1*}, Rizal Kurniadi¹, Yuda S. Perkasa¹, and Suwoto²

¹Bosscha Laboratory, Department of Physics,

Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences

Institut Teknologi Bandung, Bandung, Indonesia

²Center for Reactor Technology and Nuclear Safety

National Nuclear Energy Agency of Indonesia, Serpong, Indonesia

*e-mail: awaris@fi.itb.ac.id

Abstract

The energy dependence of level density parameter has been calculated using extended wood-saxon potential. The extended version of potential has deep well parameter that is independent to the nucleon density. The potential is pure central interaction. Although the potential is different from mean field theory, it gives the better result than that of the reference input parameter library-2 (RIPL-2). The application of the level density parameter results in small discrepancies from ENDF results. This method has been adopted in example for calculating fission products of Pu-238.

Keywords: Level density parameter, Extended wood-saxon potential, Fission products, Pu-238

1. Introduction

In statistical mechanics calculation, such as evaporation model of nuclear reaction, spallation neutron measurements and studies of intermediate-energy heavy ion collision, level density plays an important role¹⁻³. There are theoretical approaches have been developed to study the level density⁴⁻⁶. Parameter that holds very important role in the level density is level density parameter⁷. The commonly used of the level density parameter is an energy dependence parameter⁸⁻⁹.

The asymptotic value of the level density parameter is reached at infinite excitation energy¹⁰. Variation value is influenced by shell correction approach. Highly excitation state gives small variation of level density parameter values. The shell correction emerges as an effect of difference between the experimental nuclear mass and the semi empirical nuclear mass¹¹.

In the level density study, the semi empirical nuclear mass is influenced mainly by pair and shell correction. In the shell correction, fission barrier determines the variation of an eigen energy to smooth curve parts. In order to transfer the problem to become modest, the simple potential is usually chosen, such as an infinite square well or harmonic oscillator. The standard wood-saxon potential is one of the simple potential that commonly used for this purpose. However, the skin depth of this potential should be chosen randomly.

In order to overcome the later burden, an extended wood-saxon potential has been proposed for the present study. The extended wood-saxon potential is complex potential; hence the calculation needs numerical treatment. To reduce this complexity, the smooth curve calculation uses Gauss-Hermite folding technique¹².

2. Formulation

The energy dependence of the level density is approximated by the formula¹³:

$$a(A, Z, U) = \tilde{a}(A) \left\{ 1 + \frac{\delta E}{U} (1 - \exp(-\gamma U)) \right\} \quad (1)$$

\tilde{a} parameter is the asymptotic value at infinite excitation energy U . There are three-semi empirical formulas of \tilde{a} ¹⁴. In this paper the Iljinov formula has been chosen as the asymptotic parameter.

$$\tilde{a}(A) = 0.114A + 0.098A^{\frac{2}{3}} \quad (2)$$

U is the value of excitation energy that was approximated by the following equation¹⁵:

$$U = a_c t_c \quad (3)$$

and t_c is the critical temperature.

$$t_c = 0.567\Delta$$

$$\Delta = \frac{12}{\sqrt{A}}$$

The semi empirical level density parameter a_c has been proposed by Gilbert-Cameron⁴.

$$a_c = \frac{\pi^2}{6} g(e_f) \quad (4)$$

with $g(e_f)$ is a single particle level density at fermi level that is $e_f \approx 33MeV$. $g(e_f)$, which calculated by the following expression¹⁶.

$$g(e_f) = \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\pi\hbar^2} \int \sqrt{e_f - V(r)} r^2 dr \quad (5)$$

where the potential $V(r)$ is the extended wood-saxon potential:

$$V_{WS}(r) = -\frac{V_o \left(1 + \exp\left(-\frac{R}{d}\right)\right)}{\left(1 + \exp\left(\frac{r-R}{d}\right)\right)} \quad (6)$$

The potential is expanded through so-called the leptodermous approximation, hence equation (6) become

$$V(r) \approx \begin{cases} V_o \left(1 - e^{-(r-R)/d} + e^{-2(r-R)/d}\right); & r \leq r_{lim} \\ 0; & r > r_{lim} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where r_{lim} is the effective nuclear radius limit,

$$r_{lim} = [R + \ln(0,618)]d \quad (8)$$

Because of non-mean field approximation, the coulomb interaction uses the point to sphere technique¹⁷,

$$V_{Coul}(r) = \frac{Z_1 Z_2}{R_C} f_C(x) \quad (9)$$

where

$$f_C(x) = \frac{1}{x} \tanh\left(\frac{3}{2}x + \frac{5}{8}x^3\right); R_C = R_1 + R_2; x = \frac{r}{R_C} \quad (10)$$

then the interaction depicted by $V(r) = V_{WS}(r) + V_{Coul}(r)$, which replace the conventional one $V(\vec{r}_1) = \int V(\vec{r}_{12})d^3\vec{r}_2$.

The iteration technique is applied to equation (1) to get the level density parameter¹⁸.

$$a_0 = \tilde{a}(1 + \delta E) \quad (11)$$

$$U^{(n)} = a_n t_C^2$$

$$a_{i+1} = \tilde{a} \left[1 + \frac{\delta E}{U^{(n)}} (1 - \exp(-\gamma U^{(n)}))\right]$$

δE Parameter in equation (11) is so-called shell correction, which is calculated using formula below,

$$\delta E = M_{exp} - M_{Calc} \quad (12)$$

The experimental nuclear masses M_{exp} are taken from AME2003 table¹⁹) while M_{Calc} is calculated from the binding energy formula,

$$B_{nuc}(A, Z) = a_v(1 - k_v I^2)A - a_s(1 - k_s I^2)A^{2/3} - \frac{3e^2 Z^2}{5R_o} + E_{pair} - E_{shell} - a_k A^{1/3} - a_o - f_p \frac{Z^2}{A} - W|I| \quad (13)$$

which all coefficients of equation (13) were compiled by Royer²⁰.

Where

$$E_{pair} = \begin{cases} -\frac{11}{\sqrt{A}}; & Z, N : odd \\ 0 & ; A : odd \\ \frac{11}{\sqrt{A}} & ; Z, N : even \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

and E_{shell} represents the shell correction, which is determined by²¹:

$$E_{shell} = \int_0^N [\varepsilon(n) - \bar{\varepsilon}(n)] dn \quad (12)$$

$\varepsilon(n)$ is an eigen energy, while $\bar{\varepsilon}(n)$ is smooth curve that was calculated from²²:

$$\int_0^N \bar{\varepsilon}(n) dn = \sum_{n=1}^N \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_n (1 + \operatorname{erf}(\bar{u}_n)) - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \gamma e^{-\bar{u}_n^2} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} e^{-\bar{u}_n^2} \right\} \left\{ \sum_{m=1}^N C_m \left[\frac{1}{2} \gamma H_m(\bar{u}_n) + \varepsilon_n H_{m-1}(\bar{u}_n) + m \gamma H_{m-2}(\bar{u}_n) \right] \right\} \quad (13)$$

where,

$$\bar{u}_n = \frac{(\bar{\lambda} - \varepsilon_n)}{\gamma}$$

with fermi level $\bar{\lambda}$ that was obtained from the following relation:

$$\bar{n}(\bar{\lambda}) = N \quad (14)$$

N describes the nucleon number, where $\bar{n}(\varepsilon)$ has the following expression.

$$\bar{n}(\varepsilon) = \sum_{n=1}^N \left\{ \frac{1}{2} (1 + \operatorname{erf}(u_n)) - \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} e^{-u_n^2} \sum_{m=1}^N C_m H_{m-1}(u_n) \right\} \quad (15)$$

with

$$C_m = \begin{cases} (-1)^{m/2} & ; m : even \\ 2^m (m/2)! & \\ 0 & \end{cases}$$

3. Results and Discussion

The extended wood-saxon potential has been applied in the level density parameter calculation. The Calculation that was obtained is compared with the reference input parameter library-2 (RIPL-2).

Figure 1. The calculated level density parameters (black) of $20 < A < 250$ nuclei

Figure 2. RIPL-2 level density parameters (black) of $2 < A < 250$ nuclei.

Figure 1 shows the level density parameters of the present work and Figure 2 illustrates the level density parameters of RIPL-2 result. These Figures clearly show that for $A = 20$ to $A = 150$ graphs of the level density parameters almost have similar pattern. Small discrepancies are taken place around $A = 75$ and between $A = 120$ up to $A = 150$ where the RIPL-2 results are higher than the experimental results

The peculiar of RIPL-2 results are taken place between $A = 150$ up to $A = 200$, where there are quadratic form in graph. The level density parameters of RIPL-2 have discrepancies significantly at that mass number range. Experimental results are lower than RIPL-2 at $A = 200$. The glare discrepancies between RIPL-2 and experimental one are showed at the range $A = 225$ up to $A = 250$.

The weakness of RIPL-2 results is overcome by using the extended wood-saxon potential. Figure.1 shows clearly that our calculation technique has results in lower values than that of RIPL-2 hence they have small discrepancies compared to the experimental one. Especially for $A = 125$ up to $A = 250$, the present calculation gives best results.

Figure 3 Extended wood-saxon shell correction of $20 < A < 250$ nuclei

Figure 3 shows that the atomic mass number of above 125 gives the increasing of the shell correction rapidly hence equation (11) produces higher values. As a consequence, the increasing of shell correction value will trigger the decreasing of the level density parameter which finally results in our calculation give better results than that of RIPL-2.

Figure 4. Fission product of $n(\text{Pu}238, X)f$

Implementation of the level density parameters result is for calculating the fission products of Pu-238 as shown in Figure 4. Although there are small discrepancies about $A = 95$ and $A = 150$, generally the results are acceptable.

4. Conclusion

The extended wood-saxon potential has been employed for calculation the level density parameter of nuclide and gives the better results compared to that of RIPL-2 especially at mass number of above 150. This potential is expanded through so-called the leptodermous approximation which is a skin depth approximation. This potential has been incorporated in calculating the fission products of Pu-238 which results in a good agreement with the experimental one.

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